

NEEDS and PREFERENCES of OWNER REGARDING DESIGNING TRADITIONAL RAJASTHANI STYLE of RESIDENTIAL HAVELI

Rakhi Dasgupta¹, Rutu Modi² and Vrinda Kachawa³, Neerja Jaiswal⁴
Assistant Professor¹, Assistant Professor², Research Scholar³ and Professor⁴
Department of Family and Community Resource Management
Faculty of Family and Community Sciences
The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara

ABSTRACT

Interior design in India has gained its status by transforming from a mere architectural accessory of decorating and furnishing to a wholesome combination of holistic, design, social, cultural roots which lays the foundation and the basic backbone for a human to function comfortably. The basis of design is to understand the people, the way they behave in a social setting and their varying qualities. This entire analysis is transformed into functional spaces appropriate for the particular individual. The purpose of interior designing is to make the home liveable according to the needs and preference of the family and the space characteristics. By designing a space which fetches ones to cultural roots and gives one the opportunity to explore the possibilities in selected style taking up an area designing a space that will be used for personal usage as well as a place to socialise with friends and family. While designing the Traditional Rajasthani Haveli the researcher wanted to reconnect to the cultural roots, tradition, heritage and materials that were used before in Rajasthan as per the client's needs and preferences. For the present study the Design project was adopted. Interview schedule was selected as research tool for collecting information about needs and preferences of the client. The content validity of the tools was established and suggested modifications were integrated. The designing of the Traditional Rajasthani Haveli was entirely on the basis of needs and preferences of the client and all the suggestions given were incorporated in the designs, AutoCAD software version 2017, AutoCAD 3ds Max and Vray 2018 was used for designing the Traditional Rajasthani Haveli. Based on the needs and preferences of the client for each room furniture layout, flooring layout, electrical layout and sectional elevations were proposed for the designing of the Haveli.

Keywords: Cultural roots, Functional spaces, and Traditional Rajasthani Haveli

I. Introduction

Interior design came into its own in the 1990s as interior settings came to be seen as strategic resources. When people have real choice about when and where they spend their time, the quality of interior settings—their ability to support people in their desired activities—becomes crucial, often the deciding point. A “place” can be part of the landscape or cityscape, a building or building complex, or an enclosed indoor or outdoor setting. The word implies a richness and wholeness that mocks the design professions' efforts to carve it into parts (Coleman, 2001).

A design is a plan to make something new for people that they perceive as beneficial. Anything ever created has been designed, sometimes consciously, or unconsciously. Designers create plans for products that people want, need and like ⁽¹⁾. It is a visual look or a shape given to a certain object, in order to make it more attractive, comfortable or to improve another characteristic. It is also a picturing thing using the imagination; as to using perception or memory ⁽²⁾.

Residential interior space designing is a creative art which can transform an ordinary house into a very happy lively home. The purpose of interior designing is to make the home liveable according to the needs and requirements of the family and the space characteristics. The interior designer should be able to satisfy the functionalism, expressiveness and beauty. It is not just decorating the house; but it is the total designing of the house. The design should be such that it should be able to express the personality, aesthetic taste of the family, through proper designing of the space, proper selection of furniture pieces, accessories and furnishing e.g. light, colour texture, furniture etc (Calkins, 1988).

India is diverse in terms of culture, religion, and climate. Architectural differences in these places were very significant in the past. Rajasthan, the royal state of India, a place of royal monuments, fine arts and rich legacy never fails to impress its visitors. The state is also known for the Rajput miniature paintings, temple architecture, and monumental sculptures. They have created a much spectacular building where they used to stay popularly known as “Havelis”, which helped as a resident for the royal family ⁽⁴⁾. It is known for its fascinating folklore and rich cultures. It has gifted the world uniqueness of its own, especially in the field of home interiors. Ancient homes of Rajasthan are a pleasure to live in. These are reminiscent of the havelis of the royal families ⁽⁵⁾.

A Haveli is a traditional townhouse, mansion, manor house, palace or fort in the Indian subcontinent, usually one with historical and architectural significance⁽⁶⁾. The havelis served as status symbols for the Marwaris as well as homes for their extended families, providing security and comfort in seclusion from the outside world. It uses vibrant colours as part of its interior design scheme with dashes of it in almost every tiny element ⁽³⁾.

While designing the Traditional Rajasthani Haveli the researcher wanted to reconnect to the cultural roots, tradition, heritage and materials that were used before in Rajasthan as per the client’s needs and preferences.

The purpose of the study was to design a Residential Haveli by taking traditional style connected to the roots in this modern era. This style was prevailing and prominently seen in the state of Rajasthan. People of Rajasthan are more inclined towards traditional style.

Residential space designing is one of the courses as a part of curriculum of FCRM department. The findings would add a new element to the study for the subject and at the same time it would also enrich the data based on the related researches.

In India, Interior designers had concentrated on designing of commercial building and residences, but little concentration was given on style-based designing. So, there was a need for conducting a study on traditional style. The study was useful for the client as the study explored the different materials for the

designing based on traditional style and it had given better interior space according to their needs and preferences.

The study will be very useful for the interior designer students and as well as to the FCRM Department. It will contribute to the field of FCRM and other Educational Institution in strengthening their knowledge, curriculum and in its application to the practical field.

Objective of the study:

1. To design Traditional Rajasthani Style of Residential Haveli according to the client's needs and preferences.

II. Methodology

The present proposed design project aims to design a Residential Haveli of Udaipur city contemplating the Traditional Rajasthani style. A design project was undertaken to fulfil the needs and preferences of the client by developing designs of Residential Haveli. It was fulfilled by a systematic approach of organizing design ideas, materials and drafting 2-D designs. The design will be implemented after the construction of Residential Haveli based on the architectural drawing. The Proposed design project was conducted in Udaipur city, Rajasthan, India. The respondent who gave the consent for designing the project on Traditional Rajasthani Style Haveli. The respondent was the owner of the plot for whom the researcher has proposed a design project for the Haveli at Udaipur city, Rajasthan, India. Interview schedule was developed to find out the needs and preferences of the respondent for the interior of the Residential Haveli in Udaipur city, Rajasthan, India. The section one contains information regarding the background of the respondent. The data included the name of the respondent, age, gender, address, contact number, profession, education, type of the family, total monthly income of the family (in ₹), number of children in the family, number of adults in the family. The information collected regarding the plot was address, total plot area, total built-up area, total carpet area, budget, and orientation of the site. The information was gathered regarding the needs and preferences of the respondent towards interior aspects of the floors like ground floor, first floor, and terrace. The component includes preferences for the designs base on a traditional style, timeframe and various aspects of interiors namely wall, colour, ceiling, flooring, lighting, furniture, furnishings, accessories and doors and windows.

III. Findings and Discussion

A. Needs and preferences of owner regarding designing traditional Rajasthani style of residential haveli

The section dealt with the information regarding proposed design project. The client of the undertaken project was Mr. Narayan Singh Jhala who was the owner of the plot. In order to design the interior of the residential haveli, it was essential to have a meaningful interaction between the client and the researcher. The researcher first arranged an introductory meeting with the client and thereafter, an interview schedule was developed to assess the needs and preferences of the client. The data gathered from interview schedule revealed that the site was located in Shikar Badi, Udaipur city, Rajasthan. The plot area of the design project was 7547/Sq.ft. and total carpet area of all the floors was 3594/Sq. ft. The budget given by the client was ₹1,00,00,000/-. The client gave some specific needs and preferences for the various aspects of interior of the Haveli which includes:

- A combined Living and Dining area
- A Family Dining area
- Courtyard in the centre of the haveli
- Bedrooms with attached toilet
- Furniture designed in Traditional Rajasthani Style

Design development of the present design project mainly focuses on the detailing of the designs incorporated in the selected site. The designing of the residential haveli was based on the client's needs and preferences and the traditional Rajasthani style related interior features. An effort was made by the researcher to propose a traditional theme-based design to the client.

Proposed built-up area of the haveli was 3594/Sq.ft. The entrance of the haveli was given from the North direction.

Ground floor plan of the haveli:

Ground floor plan of the haveli comprised of Foyer (17'-9"x11'-0"), Drawing Room (21'-8"x15'-6"), Living cum Dining Room (27'-3"x21'-2"), Family Dining Room (19'-9"x13'-5"), Kitchen (15'-9"x13'-2"), Grandparent's Bedroom (20'-0"x16'-0") with an attached Toilet (8'-0"x 9'-9"), Courtyard(17'-9"x11'-0"), Common Toilet (8'-3"x10'-4") and Son's Bedroom-1(13'-0"x15'-6").

Fig1 Ground floor plan of Haveli

First floor plan of the Haveli:

First floor plan of the haveli comprised of Son's Bedroom-2(16'-0''x20'-0'') with an attached Toilet (8'-0''x 9'-9''), Master Bedroom (20'-0''x20'-0'') with an attached Toilet (8'-0''x 9'-9''), Home Theatre (21'-8''x15'-6''), Workout Room (13'-0''x15'-6''), Common Toilet (8'-3''x10'-4'').

Fig2 First floor plan of Haveli

Second floor plan of the haveli:

Second floor plan of the haveli comprised of Common Toilet (8'-3" x 10'-4") and an Open Terrace (64'-4" x 53'-3").

Fig3 Second floor plan of Haveli

Ground Floor

Living cum Dining Room:

Fig4 Flooring Layout of Living cum Dining Room

Flooring

The Italian marble was used for the flooring as the client's need was to incorporate the marble and it was easily procured locally and Rajasthan is the richest state in the country with regards to marble deposits both in quality and quantity. The researcher proposed a geometric shape combining different colour of the Italian marble to create the variation and aesthetical appeal. The colour of the Italian marble was white, black, dark brown and white brown.

Fig5 Flooring Layout of Living cum Dining Room

False Ceiling

The proposed ceiling plan had cornice of 9" thick border and 9" drop plaster of paris, and 12" down from beam bottom finished in ply and veneer. Wooden corbel of size: H-1'-6", L-1'-9" for hanging pendent lights, hand painted traditional motifs on the slab of equal and one larger motif at the centre of same pattern.

Fig6 Ceiling Layout of Living cum Dining Room

Wall treatment

The researcher proposed wall paint in beige colour of Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964), to give an essence of traditional Rajasthani theme on elevation A proposed level-1" resisted in plaster and punning finished with thekri work on ply and white paint, Jharokha with C.N.C. cut out in dark brown Italian marble, glass door with itching of traditional motif work and windows were finished in stain glass of colours like red, yellow, blue and green.

Furniture layout

The client wanted combined living and dining area, so the researcher proposed the layout accordingly. TV unit was proposed in wooden carving and C.N.C cutting of traditional motifs on the drawers, in the entrance of the room. The Dining table had cutting of C.N.C traditional motifs finished with brass inlay. Console unit was also proposed in between of resisted plaster and punning thekri work with traditional motifs. Seven-seater sofa, two ottoman and centre table were proposed of plywood finished in veneer.

Electrical layout

Fig7 Electrical Layout of Living cum Dining Room

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance from the entrance was 3'-9" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling fan-1, lights and one plug point. The Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the entrance was 11'-6" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for TV and set top box. The Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the door on wall D is 1'-0" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level. Nine module switch board was selected for controlling fan-2, 3 modules for lights (two-way connection) and 3 modules for wall sconces.

Drawing Room:

Fig8 Furniture Layout of Drawing Room

Flooring

The drawing room flooring was finished with white Italian marble. Brown Italian marble of thickness 10” was/ placed after leaving 1’-0” from all the sides of the layout with 1” thick border of black Italian marble on both inner and outer edges of the brown Italian marble.

Fig9 Flooring Layout of Drawing Room

False Ceiling

Ceiling plan had 9” thick and 12” drop down from the slab cornice finished in plaster of paris from all the four sides. Adjacent to the cornice 10” thick hand painted border of traditional Rajasthani motif with a centre circular floral motif was designed.

Wall treatment

Client wanted to have wallpaper in traditional Rajasthani theme with flowers in it so the researcher had proposed the “Chittor” wallpaper of Asian Paints on elevation A and Rajasthani traditional miniature paintings were hanged in a group. The researcher proposed wall paint in beige colour of Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964) for the elevation B, elevation C and elevation D.

Furniture layout

Drawing room furniture was planned in such a way that it had enough circulation space and had free movement leaving an uncluttered space for the family and guests. So, six-seater sofa and pair of armchairs and ottoman was designed for the sitting, centre table in round shape finished in veneer, T.V unit was designed in 1.5" thick C.N.C. cut out in veneer with 1" MDF backside finished with white P.U. paint with level +1'-6" projected drawers with C.N.C cutout finished with veneer. Sitting on jharokha was proposed with borders of traditional rajasthani motif finished with plaster of paris.

Fig10 Furniture Layout of Drawing room

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB)1 was placed at the distance from the entrance if the room was 10" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point fan, and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the entrance of the room was 2'-3" at the height of 4' from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 ampere for T.V. and set top box and switch board (SB)3 was placed on elevation A wall at the distance of 1'-6" from the wall D at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level for lights (two way connection), 1 module for picture light and one plug point, six module switch board was selected.

Kitchen and Family Dining Room:

Fig11 Furniture Layout of Kitchen and Family Dining room

Flooring

The Kitchen and Dining Room flooring was kept minimal with intricate marble work finished White Italian marble. Border of Brown Italian marble with 9" thickness was designed.

Fig12 Flooring Layout of Kitchen and Family Dining room

Ceiling

Ceiling border was designed with hand painted Rajasthanani traditional floral motifs.

Fig13 Ceiling Layout of Kitchen and Family Dining room

Wall treatment

On elevation- A the researcher proposed wall paint in beige colour of Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964) and picture frames for hanging miniature paintings besides jharokha, on elevation B- level-1" resisted in plaster and punning thekri work finished with white paint and mirror was hanged on the wall in which frame was made up of plaster of paris, on elevation C and D wall was painted in beige colour of Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964) and mosaic tiles were used in kitchen dado area.

Furniture layout

L-shape kitchen was designed in which the cabinets were made of BWR (boiling water resistant) ply finished with wooden laminate and for the handles, brass was used in the floral shape with chamfer edges. Partial ply partition with C.N.C cut was proposed top to the height of lintel level for separating kitchen and dining space. On jharokha, sitting was proposed with borders of traditional Rajasthani motif finished with plaster of paris. An eight-seater dining table was proposed and over counter basin on vanity with C.N.C cut-out in ply was proposed on elevation D.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 2'-0" from the wall elevation C at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, twelve module switch board was selected for controlling fans, lights and one plug point. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation D was 1'-0" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point and vanity light. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the kitchen entrance was 4'-3" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling fan, lights and one plug point. Switch board (SB) 4 was placed at the distance from the partition was 2'-0" at the height of 4'-6" from the bottom of the finished floor level, three module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for refrigerator.

Fig14 Furniture Layout of Grandparent's Bedroom

Grandparent's Bedroom:

Flooring

The room was finished in white Italian marble with 9" thick border of brown Italian marble.

Fig15 Flooring Layout of Grandparent's Bedroom

False Ceiling

Ceiling plan had 9" thick cornice with an adjacent 1" thick strip made of plaster of paris.

Fig16 Ceiling Layout of Grandparent's Bedroom

Wall treatment

Client wanted to have wallpaper in traditional Rajasthani theme with flowers in it so the researcher had proposed the “Florentine Damask” wallpaper of Asian Paints on elevation A. Niche was recessed at 5” level in the wall finished in Florentine Damask wallpaper with C.N.C thekri work in ply borders. On elevation B level +3” projected ply panel finished with plaster of paris and thekri work with diffuse light. Wall painted in beige colour of Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964) on elevation B, C and D.

Furniture layout

On elevation A Jharokha sitting was proposed with borders of traditional Rajasthani motif finished in plaster of paris. The researcher had planned canopy bed with side table finished in solid wood, Study table of 1’-6” in depth and 2’-6” in height with wooden cornice design finished in 18mm ply and veneer, TV unit had 3” projected wooden frame and level 1’-6” projected wooden drawers openable shutter with carvings of traditional Rajasthani motif at 1’6” level.

Electrical layout

Switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 9” from the entrance was at the height of 4’-0” from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance of 4’-6” from the entrance and at the height of 4’-0” from the bottom the finished floor level, eight module switch board was selected for controlling two plug points and ceiling lights. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was 11’-0” at the height of 4’-0” from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for T.V and set top box. Switch board (SB) 4 was placed at the distance from the wall A was 1’-9” at the height of 2’ from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 5- the distance from the door was 1’-0” at the height of 2’ from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two plug points and table lamp.

Fig17 Electrical Layout of Grandparent's Bedroom

Attached toilet of Grandparent's Bedroom:

Flooring

The flooring is divided into two sections: dry zone and wet zone. The dry area was finished with white marble in rough finish. The wet area was 19 mm (0.75") dropped to avoid water to overflow in the dry area and the wet area flooring was finished with brown marble in rough finish.

False Ceiling

False ceiling had drop down of 6" finished in gypsum board.

Wall treatment

The dry area wall was finished in grey Italian marble and black Italian marble was planned for wet area. In the wall elevation A and D 8 mm groove in the grey marble around the stone carving was proposed.

Furniture layout

Fig18 Furniture, Flooring, Electrical and Ceiling Layout of Attached toilet of Grandparent's Bedroom

The client wanted over countertop wash basin and dry area wall hung W.C. with health faucet, after the glass partition wet area for bathing was proposed. The vanity unit was of size 3'-6" in length and 2'-6" in height with C.N.C cutting in the ply and laminate.

Electrical layout

Switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 9" from the entrance at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, spot lights and ceiling light. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was

Flooring

The flooring of the son's bedroom-1 was finished in white Italian marble with 9" thick border of brown Italian marble.

False Ceiling

Ceiling plan had 9" thick and 12" drop down from the slab cornice finished in plaster of paris from all the four sides. Adjacent to the cornice hand painted border of traditional Rajasthani motif with a centre circular floral motif was designed.

Wall treatment

On all the elevation the researcher had proposed wall paint in beige colour of Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964)

Furniture layout

The researcher had proposed king size bed with back panel in ply finished with veneer, brass inlay work and the height of side table was 1'-6".3" thick Ply partition adjacent to the bed, T.V. unit was projected with ply panelling at level +15" projected drawers were finished with veneer and brass inlay. High back chair with coffee table and Jharokha sitting was proposed with borders of traditional Rajasthani motif finished in plaster of paris.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 3'-6" from the entrance at the height of 4' from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was 5'-6" at the height of 2' from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point and lights (two way). Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation A was 1'-9" at the height of 2' from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling two plug point, and table lamps. Switch board (SB) 4 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation A was 6'-0" at the height of 4' from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 amperes For T.V. and set top box.

First Floor

Fig20 First Floor plan of the Haveli

*Home Theatre:***Fig21 Furniture Layout of Home Theatre***Flooring*

The drawing room flooring was finished in Italian marbles. Brown Italian marble of thickness 10” was placed after leaving 1’-0” from all the sides of the layout with 1” thick border of black Italian marble on both inner and outer edges of the brown Italian.

False Ceiling

Ceiling plan had 9” thick and 12” drop down from the slab cornice finished in plaster of paris from all the four sides. Adjacent to the cornice hand painted border of Traditional Rajasthani motif with a centre circular floral motif was designed.

Wall treatment

Client wanted to have wallpaper in traditional Rajasthani theme with flowers in it so the researcher had proposed the “Windsor damask” wallpaper of Godrej on elevation A. Wall painted in beige colour Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964) on elevation B, C and D.

Furniture layout

Family room is the place where the family members spend time together. It had five lounge chairs, centre table and projector with music system and Jharokha sitting was proposed with borders of traditional rajasthani motif finished in plaster of paris.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance from the entrance of 1'-0" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the entrance was 5'-0" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for TV, set top box and for home theatre system. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation B was 1'-9" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two plug point, and lights.

Son's bedroom- 2:

Fig22 Furniture Layout of Son's bedroom- 2

Flooring

The flooring was finished in white Italian marble with a 3" wide double lined border of brown Italian marble.

False Ceiling

Ceiling plan had 9" thick and 12" drop down from the slab cornice finished in plaster of paris from all the four sides. Adjacent to the cornice hand painted border of traditional Rajasthani motif with a centre circular floral motif was designed.

Wall treatment

On all the elevation the researcher had proposed wall paint in beige colour of Asian Paints Bonewhite (code: 0964)

Furniture layout

The researcher had proposed king size bed with back panel in ply finished with veneer, brass inlay work and side table of height of 1'-6". Level +18" projected TV unit in wood with brass inlay and top finished in white P.U. paint and Study table was finished in veneer.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 1' from the entrance at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation D was 9'-10" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for TV and set top box. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall C was 4'-0" at the height of 3'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling 2 plug points, table light. Switch board (SB) 4 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation B was 1'-9" at the height of 2'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights (two way connection). Switch board (SB) 5 was placed at the distance from the door in wall elevation A was 1'-9" at the height of 2'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two plug point and table light.

Attached toilet of Son's Bedroom-2:

Fig23 Furniture, Flooring, Electrical and Ceiling Layout of Attached toilet of Son's Bedroom-2

Flooring

The flooring is divided into two sections: dry zone and wet zone. The dry area was finished with white marble in rough finish. The wet area was 19 mm (0.75") dropped to avoid water to overflow in the dry area and the wet area flooring was finished with brown marble in rough finish.

False Ceiling

False ceiling had drop down of 6" finished in gypsum board.

Wall treatment

The dry area wall was finished in grey Italian marble and black Italian marble was planned for wet area. In the wall elevation A and D 8 mm groove in the grey marble around the stone carving was proposed.

Furniture layout

The client wanted over countertop wash basin and dry area wall hung W.C. with health faucet, after the glass partition wet area for bathing was proposed. The vanity unit was of size 3'-6" in length and 2'-6" in height with C.N.C cutting in the ply and laminate.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 9" from the entrance at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, spot lights and ceiling light. Switch board (SB)2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was 6'-2" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two plug point and spot light (two way). Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall D was 1'-0" at the height of 7'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level one plug for geyser was proposed.

Master bedroom:

Flooring

The Master bedroom flooring was planned 9" wide with white Italian marble border from all the four sides of the plan. 10" wide border finished in yellow marble was proposed with black Italian marble diamond geometric shape, remaining area was finished in white Italian marble with yellow marble floral motif placed at equal distance.

False Ceiling

Ceiling plan had 9" thick and 12" drop down from the slab cornice finished in plaster of paris from all the four sides. Adjacent to the cornice hand painted border of Traditional Rajasthani motif with a centre circular floral motif was designed.

Wall treatment

On all the elevation the researcher had proposed wall paint in beige colour Asian Paints Bone white (code: 0964)

Furniture layout

The researcher had proposed king size bed with back panel in ply finished with veneer, brass inlay work and side table of height of 1'-6". TV unit was projected at level +18" in ply and veneer with brass inlay and Study table was finished in veneer.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 3'-3" from the entrance at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the

finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling two plug point and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the entrance was 1'-9" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was 12'-0" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for TV and set top box. (SB) 4 was placed at the distance from the wall A was 1'-6" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, three module switch board was selected for one plug point. (SB) 5 was placed at the distance from the wall A was 4'-0" at the height of 2' from the bottom the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, fan and lights. Switch board (SB) 6 was placed at the distance from the door was 10" at the height of 2' from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two plug points and table lamp.

Attached toilet of Master Bedroom:

Flooring

The flooring is divided into two sections: dry zone and wet zone. The dry area was finished with white marble in rough finish. The wet area was 19 mm (0.75") dropped to avoid water to overflow in the dry area and the wet area flooring was finished with brown marble in rough finish.

False Ceiling

False ceiling had drop down of 6" finished in gypsum board.

Wall treatment

The dry area wall was finished in grey Italian marble and black Italian marble was planned for wet area. In the wall elevation A and D 8 mm groove in the grey marble around the stone carving was proposed.

Furniture layout

The client wanted over countertop wash basin and dry area wall hung W.C. with health faucet, after the glass partition wet area for bathing was proposed. The vanity unit was of size 3'-6" in length and 2'-6" in height with C.N.C cutting in the ply and laminate.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance of 9" from the entrance at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, spot lights and ceiling light. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was 6'-2" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two

plug point and spot light (two way). Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall D was 1'-0" at the height of 7'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level one plug for geyser was proposed.

Workout Room:

Flooring

The flooring of the gym was finished in rubber.

False ceiling

The false ceiling of the gym was finished in pop with 1' down drop from the slab and corbels after the drop was proposed with equal distance. Traditional Rajasthani motif hand painted creating borders and one floral motif at the centre.

Wall treatment

The walls are finished in Bone white code: 0964 and level +1.5" thick wall flushed ply frame finished with veneer and itching on the mirror.

Furniture

T.V. unit level was projected at 1.5" with thick ply ledge finished with veneer.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance from the entrance was 1'-3" at the height of 4' from the bottom of the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, AC and lights. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation C was 6' at the height of 9" from the bottom of the finished floor level, three module switch board was selected for controlling one plug points for gym equipment. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation A was 2'-0" at the height of 9" from the bottom of the finished floor level, three module switch board was selected for controlling one plug points for gym equipment. Switch board (SB) 4 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation D was 6'-9" at the height of 9" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling two plug points for gym equipment. (SB) 5 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation B was 2'-3" at the height of 9" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling two plug points for gym equipment. Switch board (SB) 6 was placed at the distance from the wall A was 6' at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected of 15 amperes for T.V. and set top box.

Common Toilet:

Fig23 Furniture, Flooring, Electrical and Ceiling Layout of Common toilet

Flooring

The flooring was finished in Grey Italian and white Italian marble.

False Ceiling

False ceiling had drop down of 6" finished in gypsum board.

Wall treatment

The walls were finished in Grey Italian and white Italian marble.

Furniture layout

Wall hung w.c. was proposed with health faucet, urinal and 9" thick wall with Italian marble cladding. Wet area had shower panel with hand shower was proposed.

Electrical layout

The electrical layout was prepared according to the client's requirement, where switch board (SB) 1 was placed at the distance from the entrance was 10" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom of the finished floor level, six module switch board was selected for controlling one plug point, spot lights and ceiling light. Switch board (SB) 2 was placed at the distance from the wall elevation B was 10" at the height of 7'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level one plug for geyser was proposed. Switch board (SB) 3 was placed at the distance from the wall A was 4'-0" at the height of 4'-0" from the bottom the finished floor level, nine module switch board was selected for controlling two plug point and spot light (two-way connection).

IV.CONCLUSION

Our composite culture, come from an amalgam of many different decor elements. Every state in our diverse country has its own unique traditional interior style and people have their own native languages and culture to follow. Designing a space which is consequently connected with the history and past architectural and interior enlightens about past techniques and ideology of people in that period. Designing the Traditional Rajasthani Haveli, the researcher wanted to reconnect to the cultural roots, tradition, heritage and materials that were used before in Rajasthan as per the client's needs and preferences. The designs of the design project would enrich the knowledge of the learner's and make them aware about the significance of the interior planning of traditional residential interiors.

References

- [1]. Calkins, M. *Design for Dementia: Planning Environments for the Elderly and for the Confused*, National Health Publishing, Owings Mills, Maryland, 1988.
- [2]. Coleman, C. *Interior Design Handbook of Professional Practice* (ed. 1st). McGraw Hill, 2001.
- [3]. (2021) What is design? [Online]. Available: <https://www.koosloojesteijn.net/blog/what-is-design>
- [4]. (2021) Design. [Online]. Available: <https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Design>
- [5]. (2021) What is residential interior design. [Online]. Available: <https://www.smartcapitalmind.com/what-is-residential-interior-design.html>
- [6]. (2021) Architecture of Rajasthan [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Architecture_of_Rajasthan#:~:text=Rajasthan%20is%20especially%20notable%20for,which%20are%20popular%20tourist%20attractions
- [7]. (2021) Rajasthani Style Interior Design and Decor Ideas for Your Home [Online]. Available: <https://www.designcafe.com/blog/home-interiors/rajasthani-style-interior-design-ideas/>
- [8]. (2021) Culture of India. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Culture_of_India